

Effect of harvest time, drying, and length of storage on uric acid content of milled rice. Ludhiana, India.

Variety	Harvest time	Uric acid content (mg/100 g)							
		Without drying				With drying			
		1 mo	6 mo	12 mo	Mean	1 mo	6 mo	12 mo	Mean
IR8	Early	4.13	8.64	10.50	7.76	3.75	9.00	9.00	7.25
	Normal	4.13	8.63	9.75	7.50	3.38	9.00	9.00	7.13
	Late	3.75	8.62	9.00	7.12	3.75	8.25	8.63	6.88
	Mean	4.00	8.63	9.75	7.46	3.63	8.75	8.88	7.09
PR108	Early	5.25	7.88	9.38	7.50	3.76	6.00	9.38	6.38
	Normal	4.50	7.50	9.00	7.00	3.75	6.38	7.50	5.88
	Late	4.50	6.75	10.13	7.13	3.74	6.75	7.50	6.00
	Mean	4.75	7.38	9.50	7.21	3.75	6.38	8.13	6.09
Basmati 370	Early	3.75	4.50	7.13	5.13	3.75	6.00	6.75	5.50
	Normal	4.88	6.75	7.13	6.25	3.75	6.00	7.13	5.63
	Late	4.50	6.00	6.38	5.63	3.38	5.63	6.00	5.00
	Mean	4.38	5.75	6.88	5.67	3.63	5.88	6.63	5.38

LSD (0.05) Harvest time = ns. Drying = 0.30.
Storage time = 0.36. Varieties = 0.36.

storage and was higher in samples stored without drying.

IR8 had higher uric acid content than PR108 and Basmati 370.

The predominant insect species found were *Corcyra cephalonica*, *Sitophilus oryzae*, and *Sitotroga cerealella*. □

The International Azolla Newsletter is published for researchers in the development and application of azolla in rice production. Its content focuses on discussions of current issues; it does not publish research reports. For more information, write Dr. I. Watanabe, Azolla Newsletter editor, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Farming systems

Establishing wheat with minimal tillage and irrigation after rice

B. Mazumdar, N. R. Das, and B. N. Chatterjee, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, Nadia, West Bengal, India

We grew rice - wheat - jute in a 2-yr field experiment 1983-85 in a low-lying field. IR579 rice (120 d duration) was grown in both wet seasons, direct seeded and transplanted, with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. UP-262 wheat (120 d duration) was grown with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha immediately after rice (mid-Nov) with two levels of irrigation and four levels of tillage. Rupali jute (90 d duration for fiber) was sown in mid-Apr with 50-25-25 kg NPK/ha and fiber was measured the third wk of Jun for direct seeded rice and Jul for transplanted rice.

The experiment was laid out in a split-split-plot design, with rice in the main plot, irrigated wheat in the subplot, and wheat tillage after rice in the sub-subplot, with four replications. The soil of the experimental site (22.39° N, 88.54° E) was alluvial, with 0.55%

Effect of rice planting method, irrigation, and tillage in wheat after rice on yields of rice, wheat, and jute in West Bengal, India, 1983-85.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Rice ^a	Wheat	Jute	Total
<i>Rice planting method</i>				
Broadcast	1.8	2.8	0.7	5.3
Transplanted	2.4	2.2	0.8	5.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Tillage^b for wheat after rice</i>				
No tillage	2.9	2.0	0.7	5.6
Minimum tillage	2.9	2.6	0.8	6.3
Normal tillage	3.0	2.8	0.7	6.5
Irrigation + normal tillage	2.9	2.4	0.7	6.1
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	
<i>Irrigation in wheat</i>				
At crown root initiation + flowering	3.1	2.4	0.8	6.3
At crown root initiation, late tillering, flowering, milk stage	2.8	2.5	0.7	6.0
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	-

^a Av of 2 yr. ^b No tillage = soil between rice rows opened with hand-drawn tine. Minimum tillage = 2 plowings with bullock, lengthwise and crosswise, followed by laddering. Normal tillage = 4 plowings with bullock, lengthwise and crosswise, followed by laddering.

organic C, 16 kg P/ha, 21 kg K/ha, and pH 6.9.

Broadcast and transplanted rice yields did not significantly differ (see table).

The cumulative effect of tillage and irrigation in wheat also did not significantly affect rice yield.

Wheat grain yields after rice, rice planting method, tillage operation, and irrigation did not differ significantly.

Jute fiber yield did not differ significantly with tillage and irrigation in preceding wheat.

In total production, transplanted rice was better than direct seeded. Four plowings and two plowings were equally good for wheat, but two irrigations were better than four irrigations. □

A rice-based intercropping sequence for Vindhyan red loam soils of eastern Uttar Pradesh

S. N. Prasad, J. P. Singh, K. Singh, and M. Singh, Agronomy Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005, India

Potential annual yield of crops on well-drained Vindhyan red soils (based on water availability and soil waterholding capacity) is estimated at 2-4 t/ha. But actual production is only 0.5-1 t/ha. The wet season is the main cropping season and upland rice occupies most of the area.

Table 1. Grain and rice equivalent yields as sole crop and intercrop. Varanasi, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)							
	Rice		Intercrop		Rice equivalent		Net return (US\$)	
	1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986
Sole rice in 30-cm rows	2.20	1.60	—	—	2.20	1.60	153.45	63.15
Sole rice in paired rows (20+40 cm)	2.20	1.50	—	—	2.20	1.50	149.92	57.35
Sole pigeonpea in 60-cm rows	—	—	0.77	0.69	1.70	1.60	128.60	104.41
Sole black gram in 30-cm rows	—	—	0.91	0.75	1.80	1.50	135.00	87.94
Sole sesame in 30-cm rows	—	—	0.56	0.47	1.70	1.50	141.69	99.26
Rice + pigeonpea (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.00	0.70	0.44	0.38	2.01	1.57	123.89	58.89
Rice + black gram (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.30	0.87	0.55	0.43	2.40	1.73	201.32	103.45
Rice + sesame (1:1) in 30-cm rows	0.74	0.53	0.36	0.26	1.88	1.33	136.17	57.64
Paired rows rice + pigeonpea (2:1)	1.66	1.04	0.24	0.19	2.22	1.50	112.27	8.75
Paired rows rice + black gram (2:1)	2.10	1.48	0.41	0.38	2.92	2.24	228.75	132.42
Paired rows rice + sesame (2:1)	0.92	0.63	0.32	0.23	1.93	1.37	97.86	10.29
LSD (0.05)	0.095	0.065	—	—	0.127	0.095	14.85	13.30

The red loam soils offer the possibility of companion pulses or oil seed crops, to stabilize and increase production. We tested an intercrop combination during 1985-86.

The soil of the experimental field had 0.3% organic C, 0.035% total N, 64 kg available P, and 201 kg available K. Crop varieties used were Akashi for rice, T21 pigeonpea, T9 black gram, and T13 sesame. The experiment was laid out in

randomized block design.

Rice grain yield differed significantly with intercropping pattern in both years (Table 1). Rice alone in rows 30 cm apart produced maximum grain yield of 2.2 t/ha the first year and 1.6 t/ha the second year. Rice + sesame gave the lowest rice yield. Rice + black gram (2:1) gave the same rice yield as rice alone, in both 30 cm rows and paired rows.

Table 2. Land equivalent ratio (LER) of intercropping. Varanasi, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	LEK ^a	
	1985	1986
Rice + pigeonpea (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.05	1.01
Rice + black gram (1:1) in 30-cm rows	1.21	1.14
Rice + sesame (1:1) in 30-cm rows	0.99	0.88
Paired rows of rice + pigeonpea (2:1)	1.09	0.96
Paired rows of rice + black gram (2:1)	1.41	1.46
Paired rows of rice + sesame (2:1)	0.99	0.90
LSD (0.05)	0.06	0.07

^aLER = sum of the yields of each intercrop a) a fraction of its monoculture check.

Rice + black gram 2:1 had the highest net return (\$229 and \$132/ha). Highest land equivalent ratio (LER) was also with rice + black gram 2:1, followed by rice + black gram 1:1; the lowest LER was with rice + sesame (Table 2). Rice exhibited the highest competitive ability with pigeonpea and the lowest with sesame. □

Effect of green manure and inorganic N in rice - rice - pulse cropping system

P. Balasubramanian, SP. Palaniappan, and H. J. Francis, Centre for Soil and Crop Management, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, India

We studied the effect of green manure and inorganic N on total yield of a rice - rice - pulse cropping system in the field 1987-88. The study was laid out with green manure in the main plot and inorganic N in the subplots, in a split-plot design with three replications.

Soil was clay loam (Alfisol) with pH 8.3, CEC 26 meq/100 g soil, and 248-24780 kg available NPK/ha.

Crotalaria juncea raised in a separate field was cut 45 d after sowing, chopped and buried at 12.5 t/ha, 1 wk before transplanting rice (IR50 in the dry season, IR60 in the wet season). N was

Effect of organic and inorganic N on rice - rice pulse yields. Treatments identified with the same letter within a green manure treatment are not significantly different by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

applied at 0, 100, 150, and 200 kg/ha in four equal splits: basal, at tillering, panicle initiation, and heading. K was split-applied with N at 42 kg/ha. P was

basal at 22 kg/ha. Green gram Co 3 was raised without manure after wet season rice.

Green manure significantly increased